

Challenges in determining the global burden of non-malignant central nervous system tumors: an analysis of international incidence and mortality data sources

Authors:

Ms. Frances Dean, MA.

University of California, San Francisco: Computational Precision Health.

University of California, Berkeley: Computational Precision Health.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW
Campus Box #351615.

frances_dean@berkeley.edu, 412-996-0279.

Ms. Hannah Henrikson, MPH.

Boston University: School of Public Health.

715 Albany St, Boston, MA, 02118 USA.

hjh24@bu.edu

Ms. Rixing Xu.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW
Campus Box #351615.

rxu173@gmail.com

Ms. Hodo Farah.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

farah.hodo12@gmail.com

Ms. Dan Lu.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

dluavy@gmail.com

Mr. James Harvey.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

jamesdharv@gmail.com

Ms. Weijia Fu, MS.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

fuweijia0528@gmail.com

Dr. Natalie Pritchett, DRPH.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW
Campus Box #351615.

natpri@uw.edu

Dr. Nickhill Bhakta, MD.

St. Jude Children's Research Hospital: Department of Global Pediatric Medicine.

262 Danny Thomas Pl, Memphis, TN 38105 USA.

Nickhill.Bhakta@STJUDE.org

Dr. Daniel C. Moreira, MD.

St. Jude Children's Research Hospital: Department of Global Pediatric Medicine.

262 Danny Thomas Pl, Memphis, TN 38105 USA.

Daniel.Moreira@STJUDE.org

Dr. Ibrahim Qaddoumi, MD.

St. Jude Children's Research Hospital: Department of Global Pediatric Medicine.

262 Danny Thomas Pl, Memphis, TN 38105 USA.

Ibrahim.Qaddoumi@stjude.org

Dr. Fabio Girardi, MD, PhD.

Cancer Survival Group, Non-communicable Disease Epidemiology Department, London School of
Hygiene and Tropical Medicine.

Keppel Street, London, WC1E 7HT, UK.

Division of Medical Oncology 2, Veneto Institute of Oncology IOV-IRCCS

Via Gattamelata 64, Padua, 35128, Italy.

fabio.girardi@lshtm.ac.uk

Dr. Theo Vos, MD.

University of Washington: Department of Health Metrics Sciences.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

tvos@uw.edu

Dr. Mohsen Naghavi, MD, PhD, MPH.

University of Washington: Department of Health Metrics Sciences.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

nagham@uw.edu

Dr. Jonathan L. Finlay, MB ChB, FRCP (Lond.), FRCPCH.

Division of Hematology, Oncology and Marrow Transplantation, Neuro-oncology Program,

Nationwide Children's Hospital, and the Departments of Pediatrics and Radiation Oncology

The Ohio State University College of Medicine, Columbus, Ohio.

110 S Mary Avenue, Suite 2-291, Nipomo, CA 93444

neuronc514@aol.com

Dr. Lisa M. Force, MD.

University of Washington: Department of Pediatrics, Division of Pediatric Hematology-Oncology.

University of Washington: Department of Health Metrics Sciences.

University of Washington: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Population Health Building/Hans Rosling Center, 3980 15th Ave. NE, Seattle, WA 98195 USA, UW

Campus Box #351615.

lforce@uw.edu

Abstract

Background

Non-malignant tumors of the CNS contribute substantially to the morbidity and mortality from CNS tumors. It is critical to understand the epidemiology of non-malignant CNS tumors separately from CNS malignancies to inform resource allocation and policy since treatment and prognosis can differ. High quality international data on non-malignant CNS tumor burden are needed to accomplish this goal.

Methods

We assessed cancer registry and vital registration data available to the Global Burden of Disease study by its inclusion of non-malignant CNS tumors, reporting on the availability of data over time and by World Bank income group. We analyzed preliminary age-standardized incidence rates (ASIRs), age-standardized mortality rates (ASMRs), and proportions of CNS tumors by behavior for adults, children, and all ages.

Results

Non-malignant CNS tumors were reported separately in 17·2% (N=66) of registry reports and in aggregate with malignant CNS tumors in 18·0% (N=69) of reports. Only seven low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) had data reporting CNS tumors separately by behavior. Across all ages combined, the median ASIR of non-malignant CNS tumor data was 0·31 (interquartile range: 0·15-0·50) and ASMR was 0·24 (0·10-0·44) per 100,000 in LMICs compared to median ASIR of 3·62 (2·62-4·97) and ASMR of 0·32 (0·16-0·65) in high-income countries (HICs). A larger proportion of incident CNS tumors were reported as non-malignant in HIC data than LMIC data ($p<0.0001$).

Conclusions

Our study alludes to current challenges in understanding global non-malignant CNS tumor burden and a need for increased international data collection. Further research is needed to comprehensively investigate opportunities for future data inclusion.

Keywords

non-malignant CNS tumors, population-based cancer registries, vital registration systems, incidence, mortality

Key points

- Global reporting of non-malignant CNS tumors by population-based cancer registries and vital registration systems shows variation and challenges.
- Less data and lower rates from low- and middle-income countries suggests a need for further research.

Importance of the Study

Few prior studies of international CNS tumor burden have focused on non-malignant tumors. Most previous research has focused on incidence, typically within a single nation. Complicating research in this space, it has been suggested by prior studies that these tumors are underreported in many settings. To our knowledge, this study is the first to describe reporting patterns and data availability of non-malignant CNS tumors by cancer registries internationally over time and to present data on non-malignant CNS tumor mortality. We observed greater reporting and higher incidence and mortality rates in data from high-income countries, for all ages combined, as well as for children and adults separately. Our data, together with previous studies, suggest that fewer non-malignant CNS tumors are reported in low- and middle- income countries. The precise drivers behind these differences are unclear and more research is needed to comprehensively describe potential biologic versus health systems or other contributors.

Introduction

Non-malignant tumors of the central nervous system (CNS) cause substantial morbidity and premature mortality despite often being referred to as “benign” tumors.¹⁻⁴ Therefore, understanding the epidemiology of non-malignant CNS tumors is important to comprehensively estimate global cancer burden. As treatment may include neurosurgical resection, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy for CNS tumors of any behavior, information on trends in non-malignant CNS tumors are critical clinically, for resource allocation decisions, and for policy development.⁵⁻⁷ The WHO Global Initiative for Childhood Cancer recently identified low-grade gliomas as one of six key indicator cancers for measuring progress in childhood cancer survival, further underscoring the need for reliable estimates of the global and local burden of non-malignant CNS tumors.⁸

Global age, sex, and geographic patterns of individuals with non-malignant CNS tumors are thought to differ from those of malignant CNS tumors.^{2,3} Non-malignant meningiomas occur in higher rates in females than in males in adults, and this difference by sex varies across countries.^{3,4,9-12} Non-malignant CNS tumors compose a varying proportion of CNS tumors by age with high-income countries (HICs), such as the United States, describing that approximately one-third of childhood CNS tumors are non-malignant tumors compared to over two-thirds of CNS tumors being non-malignant in adults.³ Less is known about the epidemiologic patterns of childhood non-malignant CNS tumors in many countries around the world, particularly in countries with limited resources.^{1,2,13,14} The proportion of brain tumors classified as low-grade astrocytomas in children varied from less than 10% to more than 30% across 60 countries in a recent study from CONCORD-3.² The proportion of pediatric CNS tumors classified as non-malignant also varied across European countries in a study from EURO CARE-5.¹⁵ Together these prior studies suggest a need for more granular and robust data on non-malignant CNS tumors to discern true epidemiology.

Neglecting non-malignant CNS tumor estimates would be expected to significantly underestimate the burden and impact of CNS tumors worldwide. To accurately estimate the epidemiologic patterns of non-malignant CNS tumors, high quality international data on their burden are necessary. While malignant CNS tumors are registered by most population-based cancer registries, the registration of non-malignant CNS tumors varies greatly.^{2,16} The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study iteratively estimates the burden of over 300 diseases and injuries, including CNS cancers, worldwide, but non-malignant CNS tumor burden is not estimated separately.¹⁷ Data sources for the GBD study include population-based cancer registry reports and data from vital registration systems. In this manuscript,

we perform a preliminary analysis of the international malignant and non-malignant CNS tumor incidence and mortality data available to the GBD study, analyzing variation in population-based cancer registry and vital registration system reporting patterns and unprocessed non-malignant CNS tumor incidence and mortality data.

Materials and Methods

Our study defined non-malignant CNS tumors as grade I or II in the WHO grading scheme and included tumors classified as of low-grade or uncertain behavior.¹⁸ We use the term non-malignant rather than ‘benign’ or ‘low-grade’ due to our inclusion of tumors of uncertain behavior, as well as to acknowledge that the impact of these tumors is not benign. Disease codes considered to represent non-malignant tumors of the CNS included ICD-10 codes D32-D33, D35.2-D35.4,¹⁹ ICD-9 code 225,²⁰ and ICD-O-3 topography codes C70-72, and C75.1-C75.3 when combined with behavior code 0 for both incidence and mortality.²¹ ICD-10 codes D42-D43, D44.3-D44.5, D49.6, ICD-9 codes 237, 239.6, and the above ICD-O-3 topography codes combined with behavior code 1 were considered CNS tumors of uncertain behavior and included in this analysis as non-malignant tumors for both incidence and mortality. International Classification of Childhood Cancer, third edition (ICCC-3) codes IIIa-f and Xa were considered to include incidence of all CNS tumor behaviors unless stated otherwise.²²

Cancer registry data review

We performed a review of the cancer registry (CR) sources available to the GBD study to estimate cancer burden. The GBD study has historically modeled malignant CNS cancers by using data on all CNS tumors reported under an invasive disease code or label by any available vital registration (VR) and population-based CR data source from the years 1980 through the current GBD study year. CR sources considered suitable for use in the GBD study must report comprehensively on commonly reported cancers and ideally separate data by sex, in at least five-year age groups, and in singular year bins, although exceptions are made such as for childhood CRs, which often present data aggregated over several years. Data availability results in this analysis are presented by dataset. A single dataset in the GBD study may contain incidence from more than one CR and may represent several years. In some cases, datasets represent tumors in a single country. In other cases, the GBD study incorporates data from large reporting publications, such as the International Incidence of Childhood Cancer (IICC) series or Cancer Incidence in Five Continents (CI5) series, in which a GBD ‘dataset’ may represent data from many CRs around the world. Data considered unusable by the GBD study were considered unusable for this preliminary analysis as well. In addition,

when data use agreements requested data use be limited in some capacity, the data use agreements were honored.

We used all CR data catalogued as of August 8, 2020 for this review.

Two blind reviewers categorized CR data into one of five reporting categories using original PDF reports, and where necessary, accompanying excel files and registry websites. When reviewers did not agree, a third author reviewed the evidence for each category and in conjunction with the two other reviewers assigned the data to the most appropriate grouping. The categories were the following: (I) non-malignant CNS tumors reported separately from malignant CNS tumors, (II) all behaviors of CNS tumors reported in aggregate, (III) only reported malignant CNS tumors and specifies to exclude non-malignant, (IV) malignant CNS tumors reported and specifies to include in situ or uncertain behavior as an aggregate with malignant CNS tumors, and (V) malignant CNS tumors only reported without specifying to exclude non-malignant. If the data reported non-malignant CNS tumors separately from malignant CNS tumors so that the counts could be differentiated, we placed it in the first category. If the data specified that non-malignant CNS tumors were registered and included but reported combined with malignant CNS tumors as a single total, it was categorized as reporting all behaviors of CNS tumors in aggregate, category II. Data that specified to report only malignant CNS tumors was placed in category III or IV depending on whether it specified inclusion of in situ or uncertain behavior tumors. Datasets that did not fit any of categories I through IV were placed in category V. Because the ICCC disease coding scheme groups non-malignant and malignant CNS tumors together, if the data were coded in ICCC and did not explicitly state to exclude non-malignant CNS tumors or otherwise convey the intention to only record malignant tumors, it was assumed that non-malignant CNS tumors were reported within malignant totals. Thus, ICCC coded data were placed in our category II by default unless otherwise specified in registry reports, tables, or websites.

A more detailed review of the data in categories I and II was carried out by two reviewers categorizing this subset of data into six mutually exclusive categories corresponding to the most granular available information on microscopic verification (MV). These categories were (i) reports % MV for all CNS tumors in aggregate, (ii) reports % MV for non-malignant CNS tumors separately from malignant, (iii) reports % MV for tumors of all anatomic sites in aggregate, (iv) does not report total % MV but reports ICD-O basis of diagnosis code, and (v) has no information. We compared the proportions of tumors which were microscopically verified across datasets in category (i) and (ii) by tumor site and by sex by calculating mean differences and 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

Vital registration data

All VR mortality data available to the GBD study with relevant disease codes as of February 10, 2022 were included in the informal analysis. VR data in the GBD study go through multiple processing steps to ensure comparability across locations and to attribute non-specific causes of death to specific causes, a step termed “redistribution” by the GBD study. We used unprocessed VR data that had been split, where necessary, by age and sex but prior to garbage code redistribution so that incidence and mortality data would be comparable for our preliminary analyses (see appendix for additional information on CR and VR data formatting).¹⁷

Data analysis

We compared CNS tumor age-standardized incidence rates (ASIRs) and age-standardized mortality rates (ASMRs) and proportions of incident tumors by behavior (malignant vs. non-malignant) across all ages, in adults (15+ years), and in children (ages 0-14 years) over geography and by sex in the unprocessed data. All rates were calculated per 100,000 person years and age-standardized for comparability across locations. Analyses in this manuscript are referred to as “preliminary” or “informal” as incidence data in this study were not adjusted for proportions of unspecified neoplasms reported by cancer registries and mortality data were not adjusted by the redistribution of unspecified or garbage codes. This was intentional, to assess non-malignant CNS tumor data without adjustment by codes with less specificity to the cancer type being evaluated but differs from standard GBD data processing and reporting. These preliminary analyses were performed and reported only for the data available and not estimated for countries where data were not available. We compared ASIRs and ASMRs by CNS tumor behavior (malignant or non-malignant) across country World Bank (WB) income group as of April 2022,²³ comparing interquartile ranges. A Pearson chi-squared test statistic was used to compare the proportion of total CNS tumors that are non-malignant across sex, age, and WB income group. Two-sided two-sample t-tests were performed between the unprocessed data in categories I, III and V separately by WB income group. We considered a p-value of less than 0.05 to be statistically significant.

ICD-O disease codes are typically converted to ICD codes for CR public reporting purposes for non-pediatric specific datasets, and thus much of the data available to the GBD study is ICD coded.²⁴ To assess the impact of potentially miscoded histology and behavior combinations on ICD coded reports, we converted all possible ICD-O-3 CNS topography codes with all possible morphology and behavior codes as a part of our analysis, using the

International Agency for Research on Cancer's (IARC) conversion program.^{21,24} We also reviewed available ICD-O coded data for typically non-malignant histologies which were coded as malignant and calculated the percentage of cases which were coded as malignant.

Ethics statement

The Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study was approved by the University of Washington IRB Committee, STUDY00009060, until 11 August 2025. Data use agreements were honored for all data in this study.

Results

CNS Tumor Reporting

A total of 112 countries were represented by the 383 CR incidence datasets in our review, with data from 1980 to 2018. Of these countries, 63 (56.3%) were low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Most of the CR data available internationally (64.8%, N=248) did not include non-malignant CNS tumors (Table 1). The data reporting non-malignant CNS tumors separately, category I, spanned 22 countries. Ten of the datasets (15.2%) were from LMICs and represented seven countries (Algeria, Argentina, Belarus, Brazil, China, Ethiopia, and Turkey) (Figure 2). There were 69 datasets that reported incidence of non-malignant CNS tumors within their CNS tumor totals and were designated as category II. They spanned 86 countries, 44 of which were LMICs (51.2%) and represented 36 out of the 69 category II datasets. We observed a small increase in CR reporting of non-malignant CNS tumors, either in aggregate or separately (categories II and I, respectively), in the data over time (Figure 1). Before the year 2000, 62 countries had at least one registry with data that explicitly included non-malignant CNS tumors. Of these countries, 33 had only pediatric registries with the reports available to our study being in aggregate with malignant tumors using ICCC coding, and eight had registries which separately reported non-malignant tumors. From the year 2000 onward, 70 countries had at least one CR with data explicitly including non-malignant brain tumors, 37 of which had only aggregate pediatric ICCC reports, and 22 of which reported non-malignant tumors separately.

In the 132 CR mortality datasets in our review, a total of 53 countries were represented, 18 of which were LMICs (34.0%). Of the 36 datasets that reported mortality due to non-malignant CNS tumors separately from that of malignant CNS tumors, 12 countries including two LMICs (China and Argentina) were represented. Another 15 datasets reported non-malignant within CNS tumor totals and spanned 17 countries including three LMICs (China,

Argentina, and Colombia). China and Argentina appeared in both categories due to data being reported differently across years, registries, and/or coding schemes.

VR data captured mortality from non-malignant CNS tumors across 116 countries, 59 of which were LMICs (50.9%). Overall, our review found more location-years of non-malignant CNS tumor data from VR sources than CR sources (Appendix Figures 5, 6). All VR CNS tumor data was presented by ICD code (i.e., ICD-9 or ICD-10 coding), which allowed for assessment of malignant or non-malignant tumor categorization.

Most of the CR incidence datasets in our review were coded in ICD-9 or ICD-10 (228, 59.8%). A total of 21 datasets were ICD-O coded and a total of 37 were coded with custom reporting schemes using cancer names. Of the CR incidence data, 97 datasets representing 92 countries used ICCC coding for pediatric cases. Of these ICCC-coded datasets, two had separate tables that used custom labels to distinguish between non-malignant and malignant CNS tumors, 44 specified that non-malignant CNS tumors were excluded, 30 did not specify tumor behavior, and 21 explicitly stated that non-malignant CNS tumors were included in aggregate incidence counts. Much of the incidence data in category II was reported using ICCC coding (N=51, 72.9%). Many of the countries represented in category II data are from the International Incidence of Childhood Cancer (IICC) series, which was categorized as reporting all behaviors of CNS tumors since these data were coded in ICCC, but specific registries did not always specify whether non-malignant tumors were included.

Of the 142 CR datasets reporting incidence and/or mortality of non-malignant CNS tumors (categories I and II), four reported the percent microscopic verification (MV) of non-malignant CNS tumors specifically, 20 reported the percent MV for all CNS tumors in aggregate, and 18 reported the percent MV across the entire dataset or all tumor sites. The mean percent MV tended to be less in CNS tumors in aggregate (malignant and non-malignant combined) than across all tumors reported with a mean difference of -9.8% (95% CI: [-16.5%, -3.1%]) in the 20 datasets reporting % MV by tumor site. In CNS tumors reported in aggregate specifically, the mean difference in % MV from males to females was 6.3% (95% CI: [-6.5%, 19.0%]) across the 9 datasets reporting tumor % MV by tumor site and additionally by sex.

In assessing how the IARC conversion program handled ICD-O coded datasets, we observed that the ICD-O behavior code dictated the ICD-10 conversion, independent of the topography and morphology codes. Specifically, behavior code 0 was always mapped to D30-33, behavior code 1 to D42-44, and behavior code 3 to C70-72. In the

ICD-O datasets included in our analysis, four potentially low-grade CNS tumor histologies were variably recorded as non-malignant, using behavior codes 0 or 1, and malignant, using behavior code 3. Pilocytic astrocytomas (ICD-O morphology code 9421) appeared with a malignant behavior code across seven of these datasets, representing 16.1% (N=1015) of the total pilocytic astrocytoma morphology codes in this ICD-O coded data. Gangliogliomas (ICD-O morphology code 9505) appeared as malignant in four of the datasets comprising 54.3% of ICD-O coded Ganglioglioma cases (N=138). Craniopharyngiomas (ICD-O morphology codes 9350-9352) appeared as malignant in 10 of the datasets, representing 0.8% of ICD-O coded cases of craniopharyngiomas (N=491). Dysembryoplastic neuroepithelial tumor (DNETs, ICD-O morphology code 9413) appeared as malignant in two datasets, representing 10.0% of DNETs in the ICD-O coded data of our study (N=120). Diffuse astrocytomas (ICD-O morphology code 9400) appeared as malignant in fourteen datasets, representing 100.0% of such tumors in the ICD-O coded data of our study (N=3162).

Non-malignant CNS Tumor Burden

Across all ages, years, and locations, the median ASIR reported in unprocessed cancer registry data for both sexes combined was 3.22 per 100,000 person years (IQR 2.48-4.27) for non-malignant CNS tumors and 5.33 (3.99-6.03) for malignant CNS tumors. The median ASIR of non-malignant CNS tumors in children was 0.92 (0.57-1.41) and of malignant CNS tumors was 2.35 (1.62-3.19). In adults, the median ASIRs were 4.51 (3.27-5.94) and 6.50 (4.76-7.35) for non-malignant and malignant tumors, respectively. We observed that ASIRs tended to be higher on average in raw HIC data than raw LMIC data in both sexes combined, and by sex, particularly for non-malignant tumors (Figure 2, appendix Table 2). Across all ages and both sexes combined in LMIC data, ASIRs of malignant CNS tumors in data of categories I and III together were higher on average than those in category V (mean difference: 0.77, p-value: <0.0001) while in HIC data, the trend was the opposite direction (mean difference: -0.14, p=0.00233) (Figure 3, Appendix Figure 3).

The median ASMR of non-malignant CNS tumors across both unprocessed VR and CR data was 0.34 (IQR 0.15-0.65) in children, 0.73 (0.39-1.33) in adults, and 0.55 (0.29-1.00) across all ages. The ASMRs of malignant CNS tumors had a median of 1.22 (0.75-2.14) in unprocessed data for children, 5.28 (3.43-7.10) in data for adults, and 4.12 (2.73-5.50) across data for all ages. We observed that ASMRs tended to be higher for both sexes combined,

and each sex separately, particularly for non-malignant tumors on average in HIC data than LMIC data (Appendix Table 2).

We observed a larger proportion of non-malignant CNS tumor cases reported in females than in males and in raw HIC data than in raw LMIC data (Figure 4a). In category I data across all ages, years, and locations, the proportions of tumors which were reported as non-malignant differed by sex ($p<0.0001$) and were 0.48 and 0.30 for females and males, respectively. In children, the proportions also differed by sex ($p=0.00031$) and were 0.20 and 0.18 for females and males, respectively. In adults, the proportions were 0.45 and 0.28 for females and males, respectively ($p<0.0001$). The proportion of tumors reported as non-malignant in HICs across all ages, years, and locations was 0.39 while the proportion was 0.15 in LMICs ($p<0.0001$). The proportion of CNS tumors which were non-malignant in children 0.19 was smaller than that in adults 0.37 ($p<0.0001$). A larger proportion of unprocessed CNS tumor mortality was non-malignant in LMICs than in HICs (Figure 4b; $p<0.0001$).

Discussion

In our analysis of international incidence and mortality data on non-malignant CNS tumors, we found substantial variation in reporting by population-based CRs and at times a lack of clarity on which CNS tumor types were included in reports. Among the data available to our study, there were more location-years of VR data than CR data and less non-malignant CNS tumor data available from LMICs in both source types. The availability of data on non-malignant CNS tumor burden increased over time. In the unprocessed data, HICs had higher ASIRs and ASMRs for non-malignant CNS tumors than LMICs, with a greater proportion of non-malignant CNS tumor cases. Across data for all settings combined, informal analysis showed a greater proportion of CNS tumors were non-malignant in females than in males and in adults than in children. These findings together suggest a need for expansion of non-malignant CNS tumor data collection efforts internationally and development of consensus recommendations for effective CR reporting of this data to improve the understanding of the overall burden of CNS tumors globally.

Differences in proportions of non-malignant CNS tumor cases across countries were consistent with previous findings that showed variation by geography, income group, and an increase in reporting over time.^{2,15,16,25} The CONCORD study analyzed international data to assess the proportion of brain tumors by histology, demonstrating variation in histology, including unspecified histology, by country.² In addition, a recent study used CR data to compare malignant and non-malignant CNS tumor incidence between the countries of Georgia and Switzerland and

found a greater proportion of non-malignant tumor cases in addition to higher ASIRs of CNS tumors overall in the higher income setting (Switzerland).²⁵ Our results also corroborate prior findings across multiple countries and income settings that females may have higher proportions of non-malignant CNS tumors when assessed across all ages combined, which has previously been attributed to a greater incidence of meningiomas.^{3,4,11,12,26} These prior analyses laid critical groundwork in assessing differences in CNS tumor incidence by behavior internationally, with our study adding a preliminary assessment of incidence data availability and limitations across World Bank income groupings over time as well as an informal analysis of mortality data.

Together, this literature suggests possible differences in epidemiological trends of non-malignant CNS tumors with higher ASIRs, ASMRs, and proportions of non-malignant CNS tumors occurring in HICs, as similar trends have been observed by previous studies.^{9,27,28} These data should be interpreted thoughtfully and continued investigation to understand the root differences in trends is necessary due to the potential for incomplete capture of both non-malignant and malignant CNS tumors in some disease surveillance systems. The potential for underreporting may be greater in LMICs given data sparsity, lower reported ASIRs of CNS tumors of all behaviors, and lower reported proportions of non-malignant CNS tumor cases and deaths.^{3,4,11,13,29} It is also possible that genetic factors could contribute to variations in burden of CNS tumors internationally.^{9,28,30}

The potential contribution of low case ascertainment to lower ASIRs and ASMRs alludes to possible benefit of future statistical modeling to account for underestimation. Longer term, addressing the reasons for less data availability and potentially lower non-malignant CNS tumor case ascertainment in LMICs will be important. These reasons are likely multifaceted; individuals may not seek medical care in lower resource settings, access to care may be suboptimal, and efficient referral streams to specialty care may not exist. The diagnosis of non-malignant CNS tumors may also be challenging due to lack of clinical providers, diagnostic imaging, or quality pathology review, leading to potential for misdiagnosis as a malignant CNS tumor or other intracranial process.³¹ Even if diagnosed, reporting of non-malignant CNS tumors by CRs has barriers. Over the past several decades, there have been many changes in CNS tumor classification and reporting practices across and within countries, and CRs often operate with limited funding and staffing.^{28,32,33} As has been previously raised,² the current ICCO disease classification scheme makes it challenging to distinguish CNS tumors of different behaviors, and there is work ongoing to improve the reporting of CNS tumors in children.³⁴ International reporting is also hindered by non-malignant CNS tumors no longer being included in the Cancer Incidence in Five Continents series following version VI in 1997.³³

Further research and targeted implementation strategies, in close collaboration with CRs around the world, are needed to comprehensively investigate the barriers to reporting non-malignant CNS tumor burden and potential enablers for their future inclusion in reports. Our study alludes to the need for clarity in CR practices and reporting of non-malignant CNS tumors, which would benefit knowledge of global CNS tumor burden. When tumors are not registered, either due to systematic or operational barriers, the disease category remains invisible from a public health perspective. Thus, these data highlight that standard reporting across geographic boundaries are critical to ultimately improve diagnostics, treatment access and quality of care for individuals with CNS tumors worldwide. Previous research showed that the implementation of Public Law 107-260 requiring benign CNS tumor registration in the United States contributed to an increase in non-malignant CNS tumor incidence reported, which stabilized a few years following the statute.³⁵ However, it is unlikely that registry mandates alone would be sufficient to completely capture non-malignant CNS tumor burden, and adequate CR support in addition to improvements in access to care and diagnosis across geographies will be critical to an accurate understanding of, and improved outcomes for, CNS tumor burden globally.

This study is an important analysis of international non-malignant CNS tumor data availability. We contribute a comprehensive analysis of CR reporting of non-malignant CNS tumor data, highlighting the need for standardized inclusion of non-malignant CNS tumors and more data from low resource settings. We also report preliminary analyses of non-malignant CNS tumor incidence and mortality data, contributing to literature that can inform public health policy. Still, our study has several limitations. Data sources available for use in the GBD study as of August 2020 were analyzed, and given the time required for registries to report data, data were available through 2018 for evaluation. Moreover, there are data on non-malignant CNS tumors that were not acquired by the GBD prior to this date and are thus excluded from this study. VR and CR data sources were analyzed in as raw of forms as possible given that the primary aim of this analysis was to assess data availability and challenges with data available for this cancer type internationally. Thus, data were not processed for optimal harmonization and adjustments as would typically be the case in the GBD study, and analysis would be anticipated to change as processing steps are applied to the current data and as new data sources are added. Further, data use requirements limited the use of some data at optimal granularity, and some registries may collect non-malignant CNS tumor data that were not available for this analysis. The contribution of unspecified tumors, which were included in our analyses as non-malignant, may also impact our results. Finally, not all countries have CR or VR systems, which limits the generalizability of our

exploratory summaries of incidence and mortality results and further underscores the need for continued development and support of sustainable cancer surveillance systems capable of capturing and reporting non-malignant CNS tumors.

Our study illustrates a need for increased international data on non-malignant CNS tumor burden, particularly in LMICs, as well as a need for collaborative development of standardized reporting recommendations, referral pathways, and policies that allow for characterization of non-malignant CNS tumor burden separately from malignant to improve our understanding of overall CNS tumor burden. Our informal exploratory analysis of the available data suggests increasing ASIRs, ASMRs, and proportions of total CNS tumors that are non-malignant with increasing World Bank income status and can provide a starting point for further research into the best strategies for improvement of data capture and reporting practices.

Data Availability

Data used in this study will be made available upon request unless prohibited by data use agreements.

Funding

Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, St. Jude Children’s Research Hospital Comprehensive Cancer Center [P30CA021765]; American Lebanese Syrian Associated Charities (ALSAC)

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the cancer registries and vital registration systems that make data available for analysis and to all who are working to improve the lives of individuals with CNS tumors around the world.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conception of the work: Frances Dean, Nickhill Bhakta, Lisa M. Force. Data analysis: Frances Dean, Hannah Henrikson, Rixing Xu, Hodo Farah, Dan Lu, James Harvey, Weijia Fu, Natalie Pritchett. Data acquisition and interpretation: Frances Dean, Nickhill Bhakta, Daniel C. Moreira, Ibrahim Qaddoumi, Fabio Girardi, Mohsen Naghavi, Theo Vos, Jonathan L. Finlay, Lisa M. Force. Draft of the manuscript: Frances Dean, Lisa M. Force. Critical revision of the manuscript: all authors. Final approval of the manuscript: all authors. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work: all authors.

References

- 1 Girardi F, Allemani C, Coleman MP. Worldwide Trends in Survival From Common Childhood Brain Tumors: A Systematic Review. *J Glob Oncol* 2019; **5**: 1–25.
- 2 Girardi F, Rous B, Stiller CA, *et al*. The histology of brain tumors for 67 331 children and 671 085 adults diagnosed in 60 countries during 2000–2014: a global, population-based study (CONCORD-3). *Neuro-Oncol* 2021; **23**: 1765–76.
- 3 Ostrom QT, Cioffi G, Waite K, Kruchko C, Barnholtz-Sloan JS. CBTRUS Statistical Report: Primary Brain and Other Central Nervous System Tumors Diagnosed in the United States in 2014–2018. *Neuro-Oncol* 2021; **23**: iii1–105.
- 4 Fuentes-Raspall R, Solans M, Roca-Barceló A, *et al*. Descriptive epidemiology of primary malignant and non-malignant central nervous tumors in Spain: Results from the Girona Cancer Registry (1994–2013). *Cancer Epidemiol* 2017; **50**: 1–8.
- 5 Aldape K, Brindle KM, Chesler L, *et al*. Challenges to curing primary brain tumours. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 2019; **16**: 509–20.
- 6 Lukas, RV; Mrugala, MM. Nonmalignant Brain Tumors. *Continuum (Minneap Minn)* 2020; **26**: 1495–522.

- 7 McCarthy BJ, Schellinger KA, Propp JM, Kruchko C, Malmer B. A Case for the Worldwide Collection of Primary Benign Brain Tumors. *Neuroepidemiology* 2009; **33**: 268–75.
- 8 WHO | Global Initiative for Childhood Cancer. WHO. <http://www.who.int/cancer/childhood-cancer/en/> (accessed March 31, 2021).
- 9 Bondy ML, Scheurer ME, Malmer B, *et al.* Brain tumor epidemiology: consensus from the Brain Tumor Epidemiology Consortium. *Cancer* 2008; **113**: 1953–68.
- 10 Tamimi AF, Tamimi I, Abdelaziz M, *et al.* Epidemiology of Malignant and Non-Malignant Primary Brain Tumors in Jordan. *Neuroepidemiology* 2015; **45**: 100–8.
- 11 Lee CH, Jung KW, Yoo H, Park S, Lee SH. Epidemiology of Primary Brain and Central Nervous System Tumors in Korea. *J Korean Neurosurg Soc* 2010; **48**: 145–52.
- 12 Nilsson J, Holgersson G, Carlsson T, Henriksson R, Bergstrom S, Bergqvist M. Incidence Rates in Low-Grade Primary Brain Tumors: Are There Differences Between Men and Women? A Systematic Review. *World J Oncol Vol 7 No 4 Aug 2016* 2016. <https://www.wjon.org/index.php/wjon/article/view/976>.
- 13 Ward ZJ, Yeh JM, Bhakta N, Frazier AL, Atun R. Estimating the total incidence of global childhood cancer: a simulation-based analysis. *Lancet Oncol* 2019; **20**: 483–93.
- 14 Magrath I, Steliarova-Foucher E, Epelman S, *et al.* Paediatric cancer in low-income and middle-income countries. *Lancet Oncol* 2013; **14**: e104-116.
- 15 Gatta G, Peris-Bonet R, Visser O, *et al.* Geographical variability in survival of European children with central nervous system tumours. *Eur J Cancer* 2017; **82**: 137–48.
- 16 Chirlaque MD, Peris-Bonet R, Sánchez A, *et al.* Childhood and Adolescent Central Nervous System Tumours in Spain: Incidence and Survival over 20 Years: A Historical Baseline for Current Assessment. *Cancers* 2023; **15**. DOI:10.3390/cancers15245889.

- 17 GBD 2021 Causes of Death Collaborators. Global burden of 288 causes of death in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet* 2024; published online April 3.
- 18 Louis DN, Ohgaki H, Wiestler OD, *et al.* The 2007 WHO Classification of Tumours of the Central Nervous System. *Acta Neuropathol (Berl)* 2007; **114**: 97–109.
- 19 ICD-10: International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2011.
- 20 World Health Organization. International classification of diseases : [9th] ninth revision, basic tabulation list with alphabetic index. *ICD-9 Basic Tabul List Alph Index* 1978. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/39473>.
- 21 International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, 3rd Edition (ICD-O-3). <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/other-classifications/international-classification-of-diseases-for-oncology> (accessed March 31, 2021).
- 22 Steliarova-Foucher E, Stiller C, Lacour B, Kaatsch P. International Classification of Childhood Cancer, third edition. *Cancer* 2005; **103**: 1457–67.
- 23 The World Bank Group. World Bank Country and Lending Groups. 2022; published online April. <https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups>.
- 24 J. Ferlay, C. Burkhard, S. Whelan, D.M. Parkin. Check and Conversion Programs for Cancer Registries (IARC/IACR Tools for Cancer Registries). 2005.
- 25 Wanner M, Rohrmann S, Korol D, Shenglia N, Gigineishvili T, Gigineishvili D. Geographical variation in malignant and benign/borderline brain and CNS tumor incidence: a comparison between a high-income and a middle-income country. *J Neurooncol* 2020; **149**: 273–82.
- 26 de Robles P, Fiest KM, Frolkis AD, *et al.* The worldwide incidence and prevalence of primary brain tumors: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neuro-Oncol* 2015; **17**: 776–83.

- 27 Vos T, Lim SS, Abbafati C, *et al.* Global burden of 369 diseases and injuries in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet* 2020; **396**: 1204–22.
- 28 Miranda-Filho A, Piñeros M, Soerjomataram I, Deltour I, Bray F. Cancers of the brain and CNS: global patterns and trends in incidence. *Neuro-Oncol* 2017; **19**: 270–80.
- 29 Bhakta N, Force LM, Allemani C, *et al.* Childhood cancer burden: a review of global estimates. *Lancet Oncol* 2019; **20**: e42–53.
- 30 Ostrom QT, Francis SS, Barnholtz-Sloan JS. Epidemiology of Brain and Other CNS Tumors. *Curr Neurol Neurosci Rep* 2021; **21**: 68.
- 31 Mukhopadhyay S, Punchak M, Rattani A, *et al.* The global neurosurgical workforce: a mixed-methods assessment of density and growth. *J Neurosurg* 2019; **130**: 1142–8.
- 32 Louis DN, Perry A, Wesseling P, *et al.* The 2021 WHO Classification of Tumors of the Central Nervous System: a summary. *Neuro-Oncol* 2021; published online June 29. DOI:10.1093/neuonc/noab106.
- 33 Ferlay J, Kraywinkel K, Brian Rous, Ariana Znaor. Chapter 3: Classification and coding. In: Cancer Incidence in Five Continents. Lyon: International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2017. <https://ci5.iarc.fr/CI5-XI/PDF/Chapter%203.pdf> (accessed May 30, 2022).
- 34 Moreira D, Chen Y, Qaddoumi I, *et al.* EPID-05. A novel, clinically-relevant classification of pediatric CNS tumors for cancer registries using a clustering analysis. *Neuro-Oncol* 2022; **24**: i47–i47.
- 35 McCarthy BJ, Kruchko C, Dolecek TA. The impact of the Benign Brain Tumor Cancer Registries Amendment Act (Public Law 107-260) on non-malignant brain and central nervous system tumor incidence trends. *J Regist Manag* 2013; **40**: 32–5.

Figures

Category	Description	% of Incidence Data (N=383 Datasets)	% of Mortality Data (N=132 Datasets)
I	Non-malignant CNS tumors reported separately from malignant	17.2% (N = 66)	27.3% (N = 36)
II	All behaviors of CNS tumors reported in aggregate	18.0% (N = 69)	11.4% (N = 15)
III	Malignant CNS tumors only reported and specifies to exclude non-malignant	22.5% (N = 86)	11.4% (N = 15)
IV	Malignant CNS tumors reported and specifies to include in situ or uncertain	3.1% (N = 12)	3.0% (N = 4)
V	Malignant CNS tumors only reported without specifying to exclude non-malignant	39.0% (N = 150)	47.0% (N = 62)

Table 1. Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study cancer registry incidence and mortality data availability, categorized by how CNS tumor data were reported.

b. 2000 onward

Figure 1. Countries with at least one population-based cancer registry report of non-malignant CNS tumors

(a) prior to 2000 and (b) from 2000 onward in the GBD study. Country colors are based on the existence of any national or subnational cancer registry data on CNS tumors from 1980 to 2018 in the GBD database as of August 8, 2020. If a country had any data in that time frame from category I, it was colored dark blue. If a country did not have any data in category I but had data in category II, it was colored light blue unless the data was pediatric only or coded in ICCC and did not specify inclusion of non-malignant CNS tumors in which case it was colored yellow or orange, respectively. Countries with data in categories III, IV, V or no usable GBD data are colored red to indicate the absence of non-malignant CNS tumor data available to the GBD study. Data on non-malignant CNS tumors not yet used for the GBD study may exist but are not represented in this figure. Abbreviations: ICCC=International Classification of Childhood Cancer, GBD=Global Burden of Disease Study.

Figure 2. Median sex-specific ASIRs of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry data sources by behavior and age group across World Bank income grouping from 1980-2018. Black bars represent interquartile range. Abbreviations: ASIRs=age-standardized incidence rates, HICs=High-income countries, LMICs=Low- and middle-income countries.

Figure 3. Median sex-specific ASMRs of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry and vital registration data sources by behavior and age group across World Bank Income grouping from 1980-2018. Black bars represent interquartile range. Abbreviations: ASMRs=age-standardized mortality rates, HICs=High-income countries, LMICs=Low- and middle-income countries.

Figure 4. Proportion of CNS tumor (a) cases in unprocessed cancer registry data and (b) deaths in unprocessed cancer registry and vital registration data that are malignant and non-malignant, presented by sex and World Bank income grouping across all ages and years, 1980-2018. Abbreviations: HICs=High-income countries, LMICs=Low- and middle-income countries.

Supplementary Tables and Figures for “Challenges in determining the global burden of non-malignant central nervous system tumors: an analysis of international incidence and mortality data sources”

Table of Contents

<i>Data processing</i>	2
<i>International incidence of childhood cancer (IICC) data sources</i>	2
<i>Cancer Incidence on Five Continents (CI5) data sources</i>	2
<i>Socio-demographic index and calculation</i>	2
<i>Appendix Table 1. GBD age weights</i>	3
<i>Appendix Table 2. Median and interquartile range of age standardized rates from data sources by sex, tumor behavior, and World Bank income group</i>	3
<i>Appendix Figure 3. All ages CNS tumor ASIRs by behavior</i>	4
<i>Appendix Figure 4. All ages CNS tumor ASIRs by dataset categorization across SDI</i>	4
<i>Appendix Figure 5. Pediatric CNS tumor ASIRs by behavior</i>	5
<i>Appendix Figure 6. All ages CNS tumor ASMRs by behavior</i>	6
<i>Appendix Figure 7. Pediatric CNS tumor ASMRs by behavior</i>	6
<i>Appendix Figure 8. Proportions of pediatric CNS tumor cases by behavior</i>	7
<i>Appendix Figure 9. Proportions of pediatric CNS tumor deaths by behavior</i>	7
<i>Appendix Figure 10a. Countries with vital registration data for non-malignant CNS tumors prior to 2000</i>	8
<i>Appendix Figure 10b. Countries with vital registration data for non-malignant CNS tumors from 2000 to 2018</i>	8
<i>Additional information on data represented in figures</i>	8
Maintext Figure 3.....	9
Maintext Figure 5a.....	9
Appendix Figure 8.....	9
Maintext Figure 5b and Appendix Figure 9.....	9

Data processing.

All CR data were formatted by location, disease code, sex, year, and age group for inclusion in exploratory analysis using Stata version 15.1. Rates from raw CR incidence and mortality counts were created using population estimates matching registry coverage, typically directly reported from the registry, in R version 3.6.3. VR data were formatted by location, disease code, sex, year, and age group and converted to rates using population estimates from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2021 study in R version 3.6.3. All rates are presented per 100,000 person-years and age-standardized using the GBD 2021 standard age weights (Appendix Table 1).¹⁵

International incidence of childhood cancer (IICC) data sources.

The IICC study by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) is included as data for the GBD study. The GBD study uses IICC volumes two (IICC2) and three (IICC3) due to the years of data presented in these volumes. In each of these volumes, childhood cancers are reported using International Classification of Childhood Cancer (ICCC) coding. For registries that were known to have included non-malignant CNS tumors in their report to IARC, IICC2 and IICC3 include a count of the total number of non-malignant CNS tumors across pediatric ages in each registry and year span. Not all registries include non-malignant CNS tumors. For our purposes, we classified this data as category II as CNS tumors were coded in ICCC and in aggregate by behavior and thus malignant and non-malignant CNS tumors were not able to be separately reported. These results were therefore not included in main text Figures 3 through 6. IICC2 and IICC3 data sources are each considered one dataset in Table 1. However, as individual registries' inclusion of non-malignant CNS tumors within each IICC data source differed, we categorize countries in the text and in Figure 2 based on whether the individual registry included non-malignant CNS tumors. The IICC3 publication includes an analysis of the proportion of aggregate 0–19-year old childhood and adolescent CNS tumors which are reported as non-malignant by each included registry, for those that report non-malignant CNS tumors separately. Since our main text figures report either all ages or 0-14 year old tumors, these data are not included in the analyses presented in the main text Figures 3 through 6.

Cancer Incidence on Five Continents (CI5) data sources.

The GBD includes data from the CI5 series from IARC. Due to the timing of this study's inception and the exclusion of data prior to 1980, versions V to XI are included in the analyses reported in this manuscript. Each CI5 volume counts as a single dataset our analyses and in Table 1. Given challenges in reporting consistency amongst registries, CI5 volumes explicitly exclude non-malignant CNS tumors from volume VII onward. Volumes V and VI were categorized as category V datasets in our manuscript due to their reporting of CNS tumors with malignant disease codes without explicitly excluding, and in some cases including, non-malignant CNS tumors. These volumes have notes indicating which registry reports are certain to include non-malignant CNS tumors without reporting the number of tumors which are non-malignant. We include countries with registries in CI5 Volume V or VI that include non-malignant tumors in the text and in Figure 2 as reporting non-malignant CNS tumors in aggregate with malignant CNS tumors. Volumes VII onward are categorized as category III in this manuscript given their explicit exclusion of non-malignant tumors across all registries in publicly available reports.

Socio-demographic index and calculation.

Socio-demographic index (SDI) is the mean of three measures for a given country and year: lag-distributed income per capita, mean education for individuals aged 15 and older, and total fertility rate for individuals aged 24 and younger. Each measure ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating the upper bound for the minimal loss of health outcomes associated to the measure. For more details on the calculation of SDI, see the Appendix of the GBD 2021 Diseases and Injuries capstone.²¹ We regressed rates of CNS tumor incidence and mortality across all ages and in children (ages 0-14 years) against SDI.

Appendix Table 1. GBD age weights.

Age Group	Percent of Population
0-4 years	0.100417990
5-9 years	0.096582400
10-14 years	0.089936100
15-19 years	0.082891300
20-24 years	0.078012200
25-29 years	0.075914400
30-34 years	0.073217100
35-39 years	0.068280500
40-44 years	0.061473500
45-49 years	0.055113300
50-54 years	0.049131200
55-59 years	0.043458600
60-64 years	0.036822300
65-69 years	0.029850900
70-74 years	0.022652600
75-79 years	0.015975800
80-84 years	0.010972900
85-89 years	0.006045190
90-94 years	0.002466630
95+ years	0.000785092

Appendix Table 1. GBD study world population standard age weights used to standardize rates for this analysis. Abbreviations: GBD=Global Burden of Disease.

Appendix Table 2. Median and interquartile range of age standardized rates from data sources by sex, tumor behavior, and World Bank income group.

		Incidence				Mortality			
		Females		Males		Females		Males	
		Non-malignant	Malignant	Non-malignant	Malignant	Non-malignant	Malignant	Non-malignant	Malignant
All Ages	HIC data sources	4.20 (3.42, 5.82)	4.57 (3.82, 5.21)	2.90 (2.28, 3.98)	6.50 (5.46, 7.24)	0.41 (0.24, 0.73)	2.97 (1.93, 3.73)	0.46 (0.22, 0.91)	4.51 (3.16, 5.55)
	LMIC data sources	0.30 (0.14, 0.38)	2.82 (1.78, 4.48)	0.32 (0.18, 0.51)	3.78 (2.33, 5.82)	0.32 (0.16, 0.60)	2.15 (1.30, 3.10)	0.33 (0.16, 0.63)	2.94 (1.80, 4.13)
	All data sources	4.10 (3.24, 5.77)	4.42 (3.22, 5.16)	2.84 (2.11, 3.87)	6.24 (4.51, 7.13)	0.38 (0.20, 0.69)	2.78 (1.67, 3.58)	0.40 (0.20, 0.81)	4.14 (2.45, 5.25)
Pediatric (0-14)	HIC data sources	0.78 (0.54, 1.21)	2.28 (1.50, 3.19)	0.84 (0.57, 1.53)	2.67 (1.88, 3.62)	0.32 (0.15, 0.65)	0.93 (0.58, 1.59)	0.32 (0.16, 0.65)	1.02 (0.62, 1.75)
	LMIC data sources	0.33 (0.00, 0.34)	1.30 (0.77, 2.01)	0.31 (0.00, 0.34)	1.58 (0.94, 2.37)	0.25 (0.10, 0.44)	0.80 (0.44, 1.38)	0.23 (0.10, 0.43)	0.92 (0.50, 1.51)
	All data sources	0.75 (0.50, 1.19)	2.07 (1.25, 3.04)	0.81 (0.55, 1.53)	2.45 (1.60, 3.43)	0.27 (0.12, 0.52)	0.89 (0.53, 1.51)	0.27 (0.12, 0.51)	0.99 (0.58, 1.66)
Adults (15+)	HIC data sources	5.89 (4.80, 7.96)	5.49 (4.56, 6.21)	4.06 (3.20, 5.32)	8.05 (6.69, 9.02)	0.57 (0.33, 0.97)	3.88 (2.55, 4.87)	0.63 (0.31, 1.22)	5.99 (4.22, 7.35)
	LMIC data sources	0.29 (0.18, 0.53)	3.41 (1.96, 5.57)	0.40 (0.19, 1.01)	4.62 (2.73, 7.25)	0.42 (0.21, 0.78)	2.72 (1.65, 3.83)	0.43 (0.21, 0.82)	3.75 (2.28, 5.30)
	All data sources	5.75 (4.54, 7.82)	5.31 (3.80, 6.17)	3.98 (2.96, 5.20)	7.71 (5.51, 8.87)	0.52 (0.27, 0.91)	3.59 (2.14, 4.65)	0.54 (0.27, 1.08)	5.46 (3.18, 6.94)

Appendix Table 2. Median and interquartile range of unprocessed CNS neoplasm data age-standardized rates by behavior (non-malignant vs. malignant), sex, and World Bank income grouping from 1980-2018. Rates are per 100,000 person years. Abbreviations: CNS=Central Nervous System, HICs=High-income countries, LMICs=Low- and middle-income countries.

Appendix Figure 3. All ages CNS tumor ASIRs by behavior.

Appendix Figure 3. Combined sex age-standardized incidence rates of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry data sources by behavior across SDI. Each point represents an annual ASIR from a cancer registry source between 1980 and 2018. Data from Algeria and Hungary were omitted due to a lack of reliable population estimates from the registry or by the GBD study for the region of geographic coverage. Data from Japan was omitted because it was presented in an all-ages aggregated form. Data from the following countries were omitted due to data use agreements: United States, China, Belarus, and Turkey. Abbreviations: ASIRs=age-standardized incidence rates, CNS=Central Nervous System, SDI=Socio-demographic Index.

Appendix Figure 4. All ages CNS tumor ASIRs by dataset categorization across SDI

Appendix Figure 4. Age-standardized cancer registry unprocessed incidence data rates across all ages and both sexes combined against SDI by dataset categorization. Data from Algeria and Hungary were omitted due to a lack of reliable population estimates from the registry or by the GBD study for the region of geographic coverage. Data from Japan was omitted because it was presented in an all-ages aggregated form. Data from the following countries were omitted due to data use agreements: United States, China, Belarus, and Turkey. Abbreviations: ASIRs=age-standardized incidence rates, CNS=Central Nervous System, SDI=Socio-demographic Index.

Appendix Figure 5. Pediatric CNS tumor ASIRs by behavior.

Appendix Figure 5. Combined sex, pediatric (0-14 years) ASIRs of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry data sources by behavior across SDI. Each point represents an annual ASIR from a cancer registry source between 1980 and 2018. Data from Algeria and Hungary were omitted due to a lack of reliable population estimates from the registry or by the GBD study for the region of geographic coverage. Data from Japan was omitted because it was presented in an all-ages aggregated form. Data from the following countries were omitted due to data use agreements: United States, China, Belarus, Turkey. Abbreviations: ASIRs=age-standardized incidence rates, CNS=Central Nervous System, SDI=Socio-demographic Index.

Appendix Figure 6. All ages CNS tumor ASMRs by behavior.

Appendix Figure 6. Combined sex, all ages ASMRs of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry and vital registration data sources by behavior across SDI. Each point represents an annual ASMR from a data source for a location (national or sub-national) between 1980 and 2018. Abbreviations: ASMRs=age-standardized mortality rates, CNS=Central Nervous System, SDI=Socio-demographic Index.

Appendix Figure 7. Pediatric CNS tumor ASMRs by behavior.

Appendix Figure 7. Combined sex, pediatric (0-14 years) ASMRs of CNS tumors from unprocessed cancer registry and vital registration data sources by behavior across SDI. Each point represents an annual ASMR from a data source for a location (national or sub-national) between 1980 and 2018. Abbreviations: ASMRs=age-standardized mortality rates, CNS=Central Nervous System, SDI=Socio-demographic Index.

Appendix Figure 8. Proportions of pediatric CNS tumor cases by behavior.

Appendix Figure 8. Proportion of CNS tumor cases in children (0-14 years) that are malignant and non-malignant in unprocessed cancer registry data, presented by sex and World Bank income status. Abbreviations: CNS=Central Nervous System, HIC= High income countries, LMIC=Low- and middle-income countries.

Appendix Figure 9. Proportions of pediatric CNS tumor deaths by behavior.

Appendix Figure 9. Proportion of CNS tumor deaths in children (0-14 years) that are malignant and non-malignant in unprocessed cancer registry and vital registration data, presented by sex and World Bank income status. Abbreviations: CNS=Central Nervous System, HIC= High income countries, LMIC=Low- and middle-income countries.

Appendix Figure 10a. Countries with vital registration data for non-malignant CNS tumors prior to 2000.

Appendix Figure 10a. Countries with at least one vital registration death reported for non-malignant CNS tumors prior to 2000. Countries are colored based on the availability of any nonzero data on non-malignant CNS tumors from 1980 to 1999. Abbreviations: CNS=Central Nervous System.

Appendix Figure 10b. Countries with vital registration data for non-malignant CNS tumors from 2000 to 2018.

Appendix Figure 10b. Countries with at least one vital registration death reported for non-malignant CNS tumors from 2000 to 2018. Countries are colored based on the availability of any nonzero data on non-malignant CNS tumors from 2000 to 2018. Abbreviations: CNS=Central Nervous System.

Additional information on data represented in figures.

Maintext Figure 3.

Data from Algeria and Hungary were omitted due to a lack of reliable population estimates for the region of geographic coverage. Data from Japan was omitted because it was presented in an all-ages aggregated form. Data from the following countries were omitted due to data use agreements: United States, China, Belarus, and Turkey.

Maintext Figure 5a.

High income countries included in analysis: Canada, Croatia, Hungary, Slovenia, Lithuania, Japan, Israel, Italy, United Kingdom, Ireland, Estonia, and France. Low- and middle-income countries included: Argentina, Algeria, and Ethiopia.

Appendix Figure 8.

Data from Japan was omitted because it was presented in an all-ages aggregated form. Data from the following countries were omitted due to data use agreements: United States, China, Belarus, Turkey. High-income countries included: Croatia, Hungary, Slovenia, Lithuania, Japan, Israel, Italy, United Kingdom, Malta, and Estonia. Upper middle income: Argentina. Lower middle income: Algeria. Low income: Ethiopia.

Maintext Figure 5b and Appendix Figure 9.

Data from the following countries were included. High-income countries: United Arab Emirates, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bahrain, Bahamas, Bermuda, Barbados, Brunei Darussalam, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Greenland, Guam, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Republic of Korea, Kuwait, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Monaco, Malta, Northern Mariana Islands, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Oman, Poland, Puerto Rico, Portugal, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Trinidad and Tobago, Taiwan (Province of China), Uruguay, United States of America, and United States Virgin Islands. Upper middle-income countries: Albania, Argentina, Armenia, American Samoa, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belarus, China, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Georgia, Grenada, Guatemala, Guyana, Iraq, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Libya, Saint Lucia, Republic of Moldova, Maldives, Mexico, North Macedonia, Mauritius, Malaysia, Panama, Romania, Russian Federation, Serbia, Suriname, Thailand, Türkiye, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, South Africa. Lower middle-income countries: Belize, Bolivia (Plurinational State of), Cabo Verde, Egypt, Ghana, Honduras, Haiti, India, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Kyrgyzstan, Solomon Islands, El Salvador, Tunisia, Ukraine, Uzbekistan.